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**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**A Case Report****ROLE OF MATRABASTI IN THE MANAGEMENT OF
DYSMENORRHOEA: A CASE STUDY****¹Pandya Neha**

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Abstract

Dysmenorrhoea is the term used to describe painful periods which many women experience around the time of their menstrual cycles. 22 years old unmarried girl suffered with painful periods since her menarche. The present case study was done to evaluate the role of Ayurvedic therapy i.e. Matrabasti of Tila Taila (60 ml each Basti) for three consecutive menstrual cycle. After 3 months of medication, improvement was noticed in all subjective criteria i.e. lower abdominal pain, headache and nausea. According to Ayurvedic classics, dysmenorrhoea can be correlated with Kashtartava as Vatapradhana Vyadhi which has Rajah-Kriccha as a main symptom. The line of treatment was followed in this case was to treat the provoked Vata Dosha. There were no adverse effects found during the Ayurvedic treatment.

Keywords: Ayurvedic drugs, Dysmenorrhoea, Kashtartava, Matrabasti, Tila Taila, Vata Dosha.

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INTRODUCTION:

Dysmenorrhoea is the term used to describe painful periods. Period pain from first period or shortly after, and without a specific cause, is known as primary dysmenorrhoea. Period pain caused by certain reproductive disorders, such as endometriosis, adenomyosis or fibroids, is known as secondary dysmenorrhoea. Treatment options in allopath for primary dysmenorrhoea include pain-relieving medication, anti-inflammatory medication, the oral combined contraceptive pill, heat (such as a hot water bottle), regular exercise and relaxation techniques. With primary dysmenorrhoea, the uterine lining produces hormone-like substances (prostaglandins) that cause the muscle of the uterus to contract strongly, causing pain and reducing blood flow to the uterus. Women of any age can experience painful periods and some women find periods are no longer painful after pregnancy and childbirth [1].

Symptoms of dysmenorrhoea can include pain low in the abdomen that can spread to the lower back and legs, pain that is gripping or experienced as a constant ache, or a combination of both. Typically the pain starts when the period starts, or earlier and the first 24 hours may be the most painful. Clots may be passed in the menstrual blood. Dysmenorrhoea can be associated with headaches, nausea and vomiting, digestive problems, such as diarrhoea or constipation, fainting, premenstrual symptoms, such as tender breasts and a swollen abdomen, which may continue throughout the period, pain continuing after the first 24 hours which tends to subside after two or three days.

In Ayurveda lower pelvis is considered being the seat of Apana Vayu, which is responsible for the

elimination of menstrual blood, stool, urine, ovum etc. Women having constipating tendency or those who do not develop regular habit of attending the call of nature, are therefore, suggests a purgative to be given to the patient for about two days before the schedule date of menstruation [2].

CASE HISTORY:

A female subject, aged 22 years, unmarried, living in Jamnagar, Gujarat, had painful periods since her menarche i.e. since 08 years. She had mild to moderate headache and nausea during menses as other associate complaints. So first she took allopathic treatment but no result was found. The hormonal report suggested no any abnormalities. USG suggested normal uterine study. She had gone through 2 years of allopathic treatment but she did not get any relief. Therefore, she consulted for Ayurvedic medication. She had no previous medical or surgical illness. On examination, it was found that she was belonging to Vatapittaj Prakriti and there was no abnormal finding seen in general and systemic examination. Menstrual history – 4 to 5 days/28 to 30 days, regular, moderate, severe painful before treatment. Mic. /H – 5-6 time/day. B/H – 1 time/day. BP-110/70mmHg, pulse-70/min, wt.50 kg and ht. 150 cm.

TREATMENT PROTOCOL:

The treatment was carried out with the following medicines (Table 1) for three months. During this period she was advised to take Laghu, Supachya Aahara (which is easy to digest), to avoid Divaswapna (sleeping at day time) and excessive exercise.

Table 1: Medication

Medication	Dose	Duration	Time
<i>Matrabasti of Tila Taila</i>	60 ml each <i>Basti</i>	3 consecutive menstrual cycles	After completion of menstruation

OBSERVATION AND RESULTS:

After 3 months of medication, marked improvement found in all subjective parameters i.e. lower abdominal pain during menstruation, headache and nausea.

DISCUSSION:

In Ayurveda this is known as *Rajah-Kriccha* which is the main clinical feature of *Kastartava*. Ayurveda

attributes painful menstruation to the predominance of *Doshas*, namely, *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*. The pain may appear before the menstruation starts and may subside thereafter. It may also continue till the end of menstruation. The pain affects lower pelvic region and at times, it becomes severe. Her might be nausea, vomiting, loss of appetite and constipation. The sleep of the patient may also get disturbed. Impairment of *Apana Vayu* is primarily responsible for this trouble.

Its normal course is downwards and if it does not move because of hormonal imbalance, constipation, or any other factor. *Basti* is the best treatment for *Vataroga* as per Ayurvedic classics. *Tila Taila* was used for *Matrabasti* because *Til* has been proved *Uttama Vatagna*.³ *Acharya Sushruta* has considered *Tila Taila* as *Yonishula Prashamana & Garbhashayashodhana*.⁴ It is *Sara, Vyavayi, Vikasi, Krimighna & Vranaghna*. All these *Guna* make it a suitable medium, as it may itself act to painful periods. Probably it clears pathogenesis of dysmenorrhoea. It denotes that the therapy is effective in both pain as well as associated symptoms. Thus, the results suggest that *Matra Basti* can relieve most of the ailments related to *Kashtartava*. It supports to fulfill the main objective of this case.

PATHYAPATHYA:

Women having sedentary habits are more prone to this trouble. They should therefore, be treated psychologically. If she is fat effort should be made to reduce weight. Some physical exercises involving the bending of the waist region and contraction of the pelvic muscles should be resorted to regularly. Sleep during daytime is extremely harmful. During the period of menstruation, she should take complete rest. The patient should not be given fried things,

pulses and sour things. They should not take anything that will cause constipation.

CONCLUSION:

Thus present case study concludes that the holistic approach of Ayurvedic system of medicine gives relief to the patient of *Kashtartava*. *Matrabasti* of *Tila Taila* causes de-toxification of the body, removes *Sroto Sanga*, pacifies *Tridosha* especially *Vata*. There were no adverse effects found during the Ayurvedic medication.

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